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Navigating Barriers to Collaboration: Sustainable Tourism Development in the Acapulco-Coyuca Region

Abstract

This study examines collaboration as a strategy for sustainable tourism development in the municipal border zone of Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez, Mexico, where ecological and social challenges pose significant obstacles to effective resource management. It seeks to identify the barriers preventing effective collaboration and explore opportunities for advancing sustainable tourism through collective action. Using a qualitative approach, the research draws on interviews with stakeholders, including local government officials, community leaders, and business owners. The analysis highlights significant structural barriers, such as weak institutional frameworks and financial disparities, alongside cognitive barriers, including mistrust and conflicting stakeholder priorities. Operational challenges, such as limited coordination mechanisms, further hinder collaborative efforts. However, shared opportunities are identified, including the conservation of the Coyuca Lagoon and the development of community-based tourism models. The findings suggest that fostering sustainable tourism in this region requires collaborative governance supported by trust-building, equitable resource distribution, and inclusive decision-making processes. The study contributes to the field of sustainable tourism governance and provides practical insights and actionable strategies for policymakers and stakeholders in this and similar regions.

Keywords: *Sustainable Tourism, Collaboration, Governance, Stakeholder Engagement, Acapulco*

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Salma Libertad Gómez Torres. Autonomous University of Guerrero **Address:** CIPES, 16 de septiembre #42, San Mateo. Chilpancing, CP 39022. **Tel:** 00 52 7443733768

Email: torres_salma@hotmail.com

Mark Speakman. (Corresponding Author). Autonomous University of Guerrero. Address: CIPES 16 de septiembre #42 San Mateo, Chilpancingo CP 39022. Tel: 00 52 55 49679926

Email: mspeakmanuagro@outlook.com

Alejandro Diaz Garay. Autonomous University of Guerrero. CIPES 16 de septiembre #42. San Mateo, Chilpancingo. CP 39022. **Tel:** 0052 7444242873

Email: adiazgaray@gmail.com

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Torres, S.L.G., Speakman, M. and Garay, A.D.

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1. Introduction

Tourism, as a global industry, plays a significant role in driving economic development, generating employment, and encouraging cultural exchange. Nonetheless, the rapid growth of the tourism sector has also led to widespread environmental and social challenges, particularly in destinations where resources are shared among multiple stakeholders. This dilemma is especially evident in developing regions, in which weak governance structures and limited resources exacerbate the tensions between tourism development and sustainability goals (Bramwell & Lane, 2011; Sharpley, 2000).

Acapulco, a tourist destination on Mexico's Pacific coast once known as the Pearl of the Pacific, exemplifies this challenge. Despite attracting visitors for decades, concerns remain over the unsustainable use of shared natural and cultural resources, particularly in its interactions with neighbouring municipalities such as Coyuca de Benítez.

Sustainable tourism is a crucial approach that seeks to balance the advantages of tourism with the protection of environmental, cultural, and social resources. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines it as addressing "the needs of present tourists and host regions while protecting and enhancing opportunities for the future" (UNWTO, 2017). The sustainable tourism framework is a response to the limitations of mass tourism, which prioritises short-term economic gains over long-term sustainability. However, the success of sustainable tourism initiatives depends on effective collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including local governments, businesses, and communities (Dredge, 2006; Hall, 2008). Collaboration is particularly vital in municipal border zones, where political and administrative divisions complicate the coordinated management of shared resources (Sun, Ma & Zhang, 2024).

The case of Acapulco and neighbouring Coyuca de Benítez presents an opportunity to explore the dynamics and challenges of collaboration in one such border zone. While Acapulco is internationally renowned as a tourist destination, Coyuca de Benítez remains relatively underdeveloped, despite its rich natural assets, which include the Coyuca Lagoon and an extensive stretch of Pacific coastline. These two municipalities share a geographic and socio-economic interdependence, yet their development trajectories have been markedly uneven (Anzaldúa-Soulé, Almazán-Adame, Lorenzana Núñez & Saldaña Almazán, 2021). The contrasts between these municipalities highlight the need for collaborative approaches to managing shared resources and addressing the region's sustainability challenges. Ostrom (1990) and Hardin (1968) have long emphasised the risks associated with the 'tragedy of the commons', wherein shared resources, if not managed correctly, are exploited to the detriment of all stakeholders. In this context, sustainable tourism offers a pathway to balance economic development with resource conservation, but achieving this requires robust frameworks for collaboration that align stakeholder interests.

Gray (1985, p.912) defines collaboration as "the pooling of appreciations and tangible resources by two or more stakeholders to solve a set of problems that neither can solve individually". Collaborative governance models have gained prominence as a means of encouraging inclusivity, trust, and shared responsibility among stakeholders (Bramwell & Sharman, 1999). Nevertheless, implementing effective collaboration in practice is fraught with challenges, particularly in regions with limited institutional capacity or political and social inequalities (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Berkes, 2009).

In the case of Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez, the lack of coordinated governance has led to the gradual degradation of shared resources and missed opportunities for sustainable tourism development. This reflects challenges observed in other tourism-dependent areas where similar poor management has resulted in the overexploitation of natural resources and socio-economic disparity (Sharpley, 2009). Acapulco has historically relied on mass tourism models that prioritise high visitor numbers, whereas Coyuca de Benítez has yet to capitalise on its ecotourism potential, largely due to limited investment and infrastructural gaps. This

divergence highlights structural and cognitive barriers common to developing tourism contexts, including weak institutional frameworks, insufficient financial resources, and conflicting stakeholder interests (Tosun, 2000). These challenges demonstrate the need for governance reforms to align priorities and foster collaborative strategies for sustainable resource management.

The theoretical lens of social exchange theory provides insight into the dynamics of stakeholder interaction in tourism contexts, suggesting that stakeholders are more likely to support collaborative initiatives when they perceive the benefits of participation as outweighing the associated costs (Blau, 1964; Nunkoo & Ramkissoon, 2012; Ward & Berno, 2011). In the context of sustainable tourism, this implies that local communities, businesses, and governments must gain tangible rewards—economic, social, or environmental—for their contributions to collaborative efforts. Yet research indicates that such perceptions are often shaped by asymmetries in power and access to resources, which can undermine trust and hinder collective action (Andereck, Valentine, Knopf & Vogt, 2005; Teye, Sirakaya & Sönmez, 2002). For instance, residents who benefit directly from tourism may prioritise short-term economic gains over long-term sustainability, while those excluded from the economic benefits may adopt antagonistic attitudes toward tourism development.

This study seeks to advance the academic and practical understanding of sustainable tourism by examining the issue of collaboration in the border zone between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez, integrating the findings with the broader literature on collaboration and governance. The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the key barriers to collaboration in the context of sustainable tourism in Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez?
2. What policy and institutional reforms are needed to support effective collaboration in managing shared resources?

By addressing these questions, this article aims to provide actionable insights for policymakers and practitioners interested in promoting sustainable tourism in resource-constrained and politically fragmented regions.

2. Literature Review

Tourism has long been a vital economic sector for many regions, but its rapid growth has also created significant challenges. Environmental degradation, cultural homogenisation and socio-economic inequalities often accompany tourism expansion (Gössling, 2002). In response to such challenges, sustainable tourism has emerged as a framework to mitigate negative impacts while promoting long-term development. Sustainable tourism promotes responsible travel that balances environmental, cultural and social goals with economic growth. Nonetheless, achieving this balance requires coordinated efforts among diverse stakeholders, including governments, businesses, and local communities (Miller & Torres Delgado, 2023).

The following section explores the theoretical foundations and practical dimensions of sustainable tourism, especially the elements of collaborative governance, stakeholder engagement and common goods management. It examines the barriers and enablers of collaboration, the challenges of managing shared resources and the role of policy and institutional frameworks in supporting sustainable tourism initiatives.

2.1 Foundations of Sustainable Tourism

The theoretical foundations of sustainable tourism are well-established. The concept evolved from the broader concept of sustainable development and its principles to specifically address the needs of tourism (Mowforth & Munt, 2003). It aims to reduce the negative impacts of tourism while maximising the benefits for local communities, the economy, and the surrounding ecosystems (Li, Coca-Stefaniak, Nguyen & Morrison, 2023).

Nonetheless, translating these principles into practice has proven particularly challenging (Sharpely & Telfer, 2023). Walas, Szromek, Kruczek & Rončák (2024) observe stakeholder conflicts are common, particularly in regions where institutional capacity is limited. Achieving sustainability requires addressing these conflicts through inclusive governance, equitable benefit-sharing, and stakeholder education.

2.2 Collaborative Governance in Tourism

Collaboration is a critical component of sustainable tourism governance (Utami, Dhewanto & Lestari, 2023). Tourism involves multiple stakeholders with diverse and often conflicting interests, making coordinated action essential for achieving sustainability goals (Jamal & Getz, 1995). Collaborative governance offers a framework for aligning these interests by fostering shared decision-making, resource pooling and trust-building among stakeholders (Bichler & Lösch, 2019).

The success of collaborative governance depends on several factors, including institutional support, stakeholder alignment, and effective communication channels. Reed (1997) emphasises that collaboration is most effective when stakeholders perceive the process as fair and inclusive. In practice, this requires creating platforms for dialogue, establishing clear governance structures, and ensuring that marginalised groups have a voice in decision-making (Qiu, Chen, Yang, Zhang & Liu, 2022).

2.3 Managing Common Goods in Tourism

Common goods, such as beaches, forests, and cultural heritage sites, are integral to the tourism industry (Briassoulis, 2002) However, their shared nature makes them vulnerable to overuse and degradation, a phenomenon described by Hardin (1968) as the ‘tragedy of the commons’. Ostrom (1990) offers an alternative perspective on common goods management, emphasising the role of local governance and community-based solutions, which highlights the importance of trust, social norms, and collective action in preventing resource depletion. In tourism contexts, community-led initiatives have shown promise in balancing resource conservation with economic development. For example, participatory resource management models often involve local communities in monitoring and decision-making, enhancing both resource sustainability and stakeholder involvement (Burgos & Mertens, 2017).

Despite its potential, managing tourism commons presents significant challenges. Power imbalances, lack of technical expertise, and limited financial resources often undermine efforts to collaborate (Matiku, Zuwarimwe & Tshipala, 2020). Mitchell & Reid (2001) argue that external support, such as funding, capacity-building programs, and policy interventions, is essential for addressing these challenges, while robust regulatory frameworks are needed to prevent overexploitation and ensure equitable access to common goods (Wanner, Seier & Pröbstl-Haider, 2020).

2.4 Stakeholder Engagement and Social Exchange Theory

Stakeholder engagement is widely recognised as a key element of sustainable tourism (Roxas, Rivera, Laire & Gutierrez, 2020). Effective engagement ensures that the perspectives and needs of all stakeholders, particularly marginalised groups, are considered in decision-making processes (Pyke, Law, Jiang, de Lacy, 2021). This not only enhances the legitimacy of tourism policies but also encourages a sense of ownership and accountability among stakeholders (Timothy, 1999).

Social exchange theory provides insights into the dynamics of stakeholder engagement. As mentioned previously, the theory posits that stakeholders are more likely to participate in tourism initiatives when they perceive the benefits of engagement as outweighing the associated costs (Dutt, Harvey & Shaw, 2023). For instance, local communities may support tourism development if they see tangible benefits, such as increased income, improved infrastructure, or cultural preservation (Chuang, 2010). Conversely, perceived inequities in

benefit distribution can lead to resistance and conflict, undermining the effectiveness of tourism initiatives (Lovegrove & Fairley, 2016).

Han, Ramkissoon, You & Kim (2023) suggest that educating stakeholders about the long-term benefits of sustainability can help align their interests and foster greater collaboration. Similarly, capacity-building programs can equip local communities with the skills and knowledge needed to participate effectively in tourism planning and management (Chang, 2018; Scheyvens, 1999).

2.5 Barriers to Collaboration

Several barriers exist to collaboration in tourism governance, which can be broadly categorised into structural, cognitive, and operational challenges:

Structural Barriers- These include weak institutional frameworks, limited financial resources, and power imbalances among stakeholders (Graci, 2020). In many regions, tourism governance is fragmented, with overlapping jurisdictions and conflicting priorities among local, regional, and national authorities (Hall, 2008).

Cognitive Barriers- Differences in stakeholder perceptions and priorities often hinder collaboration. For example, governments may prioritise economic growth, while communities focus on cultural preservation or environmental conservation (Perkins & Khoo-Lattimore, 2020). Dredge (2006) suggests that addressing these cognitive barriers requires the building of mutual understanding and trust among stakeholders.

Operational Barriers- Practical challenges, such as lack of communication channels, inadequate technical expertise, and insufficient coordination mechanisms, can also impede collaboration (Stoddart, Catano, Ramos, Vodden, Lowery & Butters, 2019). Berkes (2009) emphasises the importance of building institutional capacity and establishing clear governance structures to address these operational challenges.

2.6 Policy and Institutional Support

Policy and institutional support play a crucial role in enabling sustainable tourism. Governments can create an enabling environment for collaboration by establishing clear regulations, offering financial incentives, and supporting capacity-building programs (Nguyen & Su, 2021). For example, tax incentives for eco-friendly businesses, grants for community-based tourism projects, and penalties for environmental violations can promote sustainable practices (Khan, Bibi, Ardito, Lyu, Hayat & Arif, 2020).

Institutional capacity also influences the effectiveness of tourism governance. In regions with limited resources or weak institutions, external support from NGOs, international organisations, and private sector partnerships can fill critical gaps. Mitchell & Ashley (2010) maintain that collaborative frameworks, such as public-private partnerships, can enhance resource mobilisation and stakeholder coordination in tourism projects.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study Area

The municipalities of Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez are located along Mexico's Pacific coastline in Guerrero, a state known for its natural beauty and cultural heritage, yet also recognised for its socio-economic disparities. These two municipalities share common natural resources and economic ties, thus making them suitable for examining collaboration in sustainable tourism.

Acapulco- Acapulco is one of Mexico's most renowned tourist destinations, famous for its beaches and nightlife. Following significant tourism development, largely driven by government investments in infrastructure and international marketing (Clancy, 2001) it became the world's leading destination (Torres & Momsen, 2005). Speakman & Garay (2020), identify four defining stages in Acapulco's tourism evolution- (i) the rise of tourism, (ii) the golden age, (iii) slow decline and an attempt at reinvention, (iv) rapid decline and

crisis. While the city has long been a symbol of Mexico's tourism success, it now faces challenges as it lingers in this state of crisis, characterised by environmental degradation, income inequality, and declining tourist numbers due to security concerns (Muñoz Sánchez, Rivas Pérez, Chavarría Solís, Arziga Castañón & Fajardo Chavarría, 2024).

Coyuca de Benítez- Coyuca de Benítez, located just northwest of Acapulco, presents a sharp contrast to its neighbour. The municipality is much less developed but rich in natural resources, including the Coyuca Lagoon and surrounding mangrove forests. The lagoon is a prime ecological asset, supporting diverse flora and fauna, and is also integral to local livelihoods such as fishing and small-scale tourism (Rosales-Flores & Olmos-Martínez, 2020). Despite its potential, Coyuca de Benítez lacks the infrastructure and investment needed to fully leverage its tourism opportunities. The area has seen interest in ecotourism and community-based tourism, but these initiatives remain underdeveloped due to limited financial and technical resources (Becerril, Rodríguez Cortes & Yañez Soria, 2021; Moreno & Torres, 2023).

3.1.1 Shared Resources and Interdependence

The Pacific coastline and the Coyuca Lagoon are vital shared resources that are the foundation of the tourism economy in both municipalities. These natural assets attract visitors for activities such as fishing, birdwatching, and water sports, yet their management remains fragmented. Overuse and poor governance have led to environmental degradation, including water pollution in the Coyuca Lagoon and deforestation in surrounding areas (Pérez & Becerril, 2023)). The shared dependence on these resources presents both a challenge and an opportunity for collaboration between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez.

3.1.2 Socio-Economic and Governance Context

The socio-economic disparities between the two municipalities underscore the complexity of collaboration. Acapulco benefits from a more established tourism infrastructure and larger municipal budgets, yet it also struggles with severe income inequality and social tensions (Speakman, 2019). In contrast, Coyuca de Benítez remains more rural and reliant on traditional livelihoods, with limited access to funding and technical expertise for tourism development (Becerril, De Coss-Corzo & Anderson, 2021).

Governance in the region is characterised by overlapping jurisdictions and limited coordination between local, state, and federal authorities. This lack of integration exacerbates resource management challenges and hinders the implementation of sustainable tourism policies (Vitz, 2023).

3.2 Research Design

This study employs an exploratory qualitative research design, selected for its strong alignment with the research questions and objectives. Qualitative research provides the flexibility and depth needed to examine stakeholder perspectives, governance dynamics, and socio-economic contexts in detail. This approach facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the research problem while allowing for the emergence of new insights (Creswell, 2014).

3.3 Data Collection Methods

The primary method of data collection was semi-structured interviews, which enabled the researchers to engage deeply with a range of stakeholders. A total of fifteen participants- ten from Coyuca de Benitez and five from Acapulco- were involved. These included municipal officials, local business owners, community leaders, and residents, each offering their perspectives on governance, collaboration, and sustainable tourism practices. The interviews followed a flexible framework covering key topics such as stakeholder roles, perceived barriers to effective collaboration, and aspirations for sustainable tourism development.

The selection of participants was guided by purposive sampling to ensure alignment with the research objectives. Key stakeholders with direct involvement in governance and tourism activities were prioritised to provide insights into both formal and informal processes. Snowball sampling was also employed, allowing participants to recommended others, thereby facilitating access to community leaders and small-scale business owners who might otherwise have been difficult to reach. This combination of sampling methods ensured a diverse range of perspectives and enriched the data collected. The interviews were undertaken in Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez between 2018 and 2019. They were conducted in Spanish and later transcribed into English to facilitate analysis.

3.4 Interview Questions

Table 1 below demonstrates the alignment between the research questions and the interview questions.

Table 1: Purpose of the interview questions in relation with the research questions

<i>Research question</i>	<i>Example of interview question</i>	<i>Purpose</i>
<i>What are the key barriers to collaboration in the context of sustainable tourism in Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How would you describe the current level of collaboration among stakeholders involved in tourism in this region? - What challenges do you face when working with other stakeholders? - Are there any specific conflicts or tensions that make collaboration difficult? - How do you think trust and communication affect collaboration efforts? 	These questions aim to explore stakeholders' perceptions of collaboration, identify specific barriers, and uncover structural or interpersonal obstacles to cooperation
<i>What policy and institutional reforms are needed to support effective collaboration in managing shared resources?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What policies or regulations currently govern tourism activities in the region? - Do you believe existing policies are effective in promoting collaboration? Why or why not? - What kind of support do you think local or national governments should provide to improve tourism governance? - Are there any institutional changes you believe are necessary to enhance sustainable resource management? 	These questions focus on identifying gaps in current policies and governance structures, while gathering stakeholder perspectives on potential reforms or improvements.

3.5 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the interview data, following the approach outlined by Braun & Clarke (2006). This method enabled the researchers to identify, organise, and interpret patterns within the data systematically. Initial coding was guided by the research objectives, focusing on themes such as structural barriers, stakeholder trust, and shared resource management. Inductive coding complemented this process by allowing unexpected themes and insights to emerge from the participants' narratives.

The codes were then grouped into broader themes through an iterative process to ensure they accurately reflected the data. To enhance the reliability of the findings, the data were cross-referenced and validated, ensuring that the conclusions drawn were consistent and well-grounded in the perspectives of multiple stakeholders.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The research adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the integrity of the study and the well-being of its participants. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, scope, and potential outcomes before their involvement. Informed consent was obtained, and the confidentiality of participants was maintained by anonymising their identities and securely storing all data.

4. Findings

4.1 Structural Barriers

Weak Institutional Frameworks – The absence of robust institutional mechanisms to support collaboration emerged as a significant barrier. Municipal officials from both regions expressed frustration over the lack of formal agreements or policies governing shared resource management. One official stated:

"Each municipality has its own agenda. There is no plan or shared vision." (Participant 1, personal communication, Coyuca de Benitez, 28 May, 2018).

Limited Financial Resources – Financial constraints severely limit the ability of both municipalities to implement sustainable tourism initiatives. Coyuca de Benítez, in particular, struggles with inadequate funding for infrastructure and resource conservation. A local business owner noted:

"There is no funding for joint projects or marketing efforts. Everyone is left to fend for themselves." (Participant 3, personal communication, Coyuca de Benitez, 7 July, 2018).

Even Acapulco, despite having larger municipal budget, tends to prioritise short-term mass tourism projects over sustainable initiatives.

Jurisdictional Overlaps and Bureaucracy- Overlapping jurisdictions among local, state, and federal authorities exacerbate inefficiencies and delay project approvals. One municipal official commented:

"Even when we want to collaborate, the bureaucracy is overwhelming. It can take months to get approval for even basic projects." (Participant 2, personal communication, Coyuca de Benitez, 7 July, 2018)

These administrative challenges discourage stakeholders from pursuing joint initiatives and further obstruct resource management efforts.

4.2 Cognitive Barriers

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Divergent Stakeholder Perceptions-

Conflicting priorities between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez stakeholders hinder collaboration. While Acapulco emphasises economic growth and mass tourism, Coyuca de Benítez prioritises environmental conservation and community-based tourism. A participant from Coyuca de Benitez remarked:

"Our focus is on preserving the lagoon and promoting small-scale tourism that benefits the community. Acapulco's priorities are very different." (Participant 5, Coyuca de Benitez, 8 July, 2018)

Lack of Trust-

Mistrust among stakeholders from both municipalities emerged as a pervasive barrier. Community leaders in Coyuca de Benitez expressed scepticism about Acapulco's commitment to equitable collaboration. One participant insisted:

"We have seen this before—Acapulco benefits, and we are left with the environmental damage." (Participant 9, Coyuca de Benitez, 12 November, 2018)

This lack of trust extends to relationships between local communities and government institutions, further complicating collaboration efforts.

Limited Awareness of Sustainability Principles-

Many stakeholders, particularly in Acapulco, demonstrated a limited understanding of sustainable tourism principles. A participant from the tourism sector stated:

"Sustainability is a nice idea, but it is hard to focus on that when the priority is getting tourists and making money." (Participant 12, Acapulco, 28 November, 2018)

4.3 Operational Barriers*Insufficient Coordination Mechanisms-*

The absence of formal platforms for regular communication or joint decision-making further hinders collaboration. A respondent explained:

"We do not have regular meetings or even informal ways to connect with stakeholders from the other municipality." (Participant 8, Coyuca de Benitez, 12 November, 2018)

Challenges in Community Engagement-

Engaging local communities in tourism planning and management remains a significant challenge. Community members in Coyuca de Benítez expressed feelings of exclusion from decision-making processes. One resident noted:

"We are not consulted. Decisions are made without our input, even though we are the ones most affected." (Participant 1, Coyuca de Benitez, 28 May, 2018)

Resource Constraints-

Beyond financial limitations, a shortage of technical expertise and trained personnel also constrains sustainable tourism efforts. A municipal official commented:

"We do not have the trained personnel or technical knowledge to manage tourism sustainably. Even when we want to collaborate, we lack the tools to do it effectively." (Participant 7, Coyuca de Benitez, 9 November, 2018)

4.4 Opportunities for Collaboration

Despite these challenges, several opportunities for advancing collaboration were identified. Both municipalities recognise the importance of conserving the Coyuca Lagoon and Pacific coastline as shared resources critical to their long-term viability. A respondent noted:

"We all depend on the lagoon, whether for tourism, fishing, or just the beauty it brings to the region. There is agreement that it needs to be protected." (Participant 2, personal communication, Coyuca de Benitez, 7 July, 2018)

There is also growing interest in promoting ecotourism as a sustainable alternative to mass tourism. A local business owner in Acapulco commented:

"If Acapulco and Coyuca could work together to promote ecotourism, it would benefit everyone. Tourists could experience the best of both worlds." (Participant 15, Acapulco, 26 January, 2019)

Finally, respondents expressed a willingness to learn from successful collaborative models in other regions. As one municipal official noted:

"There are examples out there that show how collaboration can work. We need to learn from those and adapt them to our context." (Participant 14, Acapulco, 26 January, 2019)

5. Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Structural Barriers and Collaborative Governance

The findings demonstrate that weak institutional frameworks and financial constraints significantly restrict collaboration in the Acapulco-Coyuca municipal border zone. These challenges resonate with Hall's (2008) observation that fragmented tourism governance, characterised by overlapping jurisdictions and conflicting priorities, often undermines coordinated action. In the study area, the absence of formal agreements and shared policies reflects the broader governance challenge of aligning multi-level actors and interests.

Collaborative governance models emphasise the importance of institutional support in creating enabling environments for shared decision-making (Ansell & Gash, 2008). However, the lack of such frameworks in this region hinders resource pooling and trust-building, reinforcing the barriers noted by Dredge (2006) and Graci (2020). Additionally, the financial constraints in Coyuca de Benítez, compared to Acapulco, exemplify resource disparities that affect collaborative policymaking (Bramwell & Sharman, 1999). These disparities further exacerbate power imbalances and prevent equitable benefit-sharing, limiting the feasibility of joint initiatives.

The findings underscore the critical need for institutional capacity-building, regulatory reform, and external funding to address structural barriers (Nguyen & Su, 2021). Public-private partnerships, as suggested by Mitchell & Ashley (2010), could serve as a viable solution for resource mobilisation and stakeholder alignment in the region.

5.2 Cognitive Barriers and Stakeholder Perceptions

The study highlights divergent stakeholder priorities as a major cognitive barrier, with Acapulco prioritising mass tourism and economic growth, while Coyuca de Benítez emphasises environmental conservation and community-based tourism. This finding aligns with Dredge's (2006) assertion that differences in stakeholder values often hinder collaboration, particularly when economic imperatives conflict with sustainability goals.

Social exchange theory provides a theoretical lens for understanding these dynamics. As Dutt et al., (2023) insist, stakeholders are more likely to engage in collaborative initiatives when they perceive that the benefits outweigh the costs. However, in this context, perceptions of inequitable benefit distribution undermine the willingness to collaborate. Residents of

Coyuca de Benítez, who have historically seen limited economic benefits from tourism, expressed scepticism toward partnerships with Acapulco, a finding that resonates with Tosun's (2000) research on the marginalisation of local communities in tourism governance.

The findings also emphasise that lack of trust is a critical cognitive barrier. Ansell & Gash (2008) highlight its importance for collaborative governance, yet historical grievances and perceived exploitation by Acapulco have eroded stakeholder confidence in Coyuca de Benítez. This is consistent with Reed's (1997) observation that power imbalances and lack of transparency impede trust-building. Addressing this barrier requires not only fostering inclusive dialogue but also implementing mechanisms for equitable benefit-sharing to rebuild trust (Timothy, 1999).

5.3 Operational Barriers and Common Goods Management

Operational barriers, such as inadequate coordination mechanisms and community disengagement, emerged as significant challenges in the study. These findings support Ostrom's (1990) framework on common goods, which underscores the importance of collective action and locally tailored governance structures in managing shared resources. The lack of formal coordination mechanisms in the Acapulco-Coyuca de Benitez zone prevents effective management of common goods- such as the Coyuca Lagoon- which serves to emphasise Hardin's (1968) concept of the 'tragedy of the commons.'

The exclusion of local communities from decision-making processes further exacerbates operational challenges. Community participation is essential for fostering a sense of ownership and accountability in tourism governance (Scheyvens, 1999). In Coyuca de Benítez, the marginalisation of community voices has led to apathy and resistance, undermining collaborative efforts. This finding supports Stoddart et al.'s (2019) argument that capacity-building programmes and clear governance structures are essential for enhancing stakeholder engagement. Additionally, the lack of communication channels and participatory frameworks to address operational barriers underscores the urgent need for institutional reforms that prioritise inclusivity and transparency (Berkes, 2009; Qiu et al., 2022).

5.4 Opportunities for Collaboration: Shared Interests and Sustainable Models

Despite several barriers, the findings reveal shared interests in conserving the Coyuca Lagoon and Pacific coastline, presenting opportunities for collaboration. This aligns with Ostrom's (1990) assertion that mutual recognition of interdependence is a key enabler of collective action. Both municipalities recognise the ecological and economic importance of these shared resources, providing a foundation for joint conservation initiatives.

The growing interest in community-based tourism models in Coyuca de Benítez represents another opportunity for collaboration. As Roxas et al., (2020) suggest, low-impact tourism models can generate economic benefits while preserving natural and cultural assets. Collaborative marketing campaigns that position the region as an integrated sustainable tourism destination could appeal to environmentally conscious travellers, benefitting both municipalities.

Learning from successful models in other regions could further support collaborative efforts. For example, participatory governance frameworks in Nepal's Annapurna Conservation Area and Costa Rica's Monteverde Cloud Forest demonstrate how community involvement and institutional support can balance resource conservation with tourism development (Berkes, 2009; Weaver, 2001). Adapting these practices to the Acapulco-Coyuca context could help overcome barriers and leverage shared opportunities.

5.5 Theoretical Implications

The findings contribute to the theoretical discourse on sustainable tourism governance in several ways:

Expanding Collaborative Governance Models: The study underscores the need to incorporate historical and socio-political dimensions into existing models of collaborative governance. While frameworks such as Ansell & Gash (2008) emphasise trust, shared goals, and institutional capacity, the findings highlight the role of historical grievances and power imbalances in shaping stakeholder dynamics. Integrating these factors could enhance the applicability of collaborative governance models to regions with complex socio-economic contexts.

Enhancing Social Exchange Theory: The findings contribute to social exchange theory by emphasising the collective nature of benefits and costs in managing common goods. Unlike individual exchanges, collaborative tourism governance involves multi-stakeholder dynamics, where perceptions of fairness and equity play a central role. Addressing these perceptions is critical for fostering collaboration in resource-dependent regions (Dutt et al., 2023).

Reconceptualising Community Engagement: The exclusion of local communities from decision-making processes serves to demonstrate the limitations of top-down governance approaches. The study supports calls for a reconceptualisation of community engagement frameworks, emphasising the need for genuine participation and empowerment of marginalised stakeholders (Garrod, 2003; Scheyvens, 1999) Integrating mechanisms for equitable benefit-sharing and capacity-building into these frameworks could enhance their effectiveness.

Linking Structural and Operational Challenges: The intersection of structural and operational barriers observed in this study reinforces the need for integrated approaches to sustainable tourism governance. Theoretical models should address the interplay between institutional capacity, stakeholder dynamics, and on-the-ground coordination challenges to provide a more holistic understanding of governance in tourism contexts.

Table 2 below summarises the barriers and opportunities for collaboration in sustainable tourism governance. It categorises the findings into structural, cognitive, and operational barriers, as well as opportunities for collaboration. Each category is linked to specific findings and discussed in relation to theoretical frameworks or practical implications for sustainable tourism.

Table 2: Barriers and Opportunities for Sustainable Tourism Collaboration in the Acapulco-Coyuca Border Zone

<i>Category</i>	<i>Findings</i>	<i>Discussion</i>
<i>Structural Barriers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weak institutional frameworks: No formal agreements or policies. - Limited financial resources: Coyuca struggles with funding; Acapulco prioritises short-term projects. - Jurisdictional overlaps and bureaucracy delay approvals. 	Emphasises the need for institutional capacity-building, regulatory reform, and external funding. Public-private partnerships can mobilise resources and align stakeholders. Aligns with Ansell & Gash (2008) and Dredge (2006) frameworks for collaborative governance.
<i>Cognitive Barriers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Divergent priorities: Acapulco focuses on mass tourism; Coyuca prioritises environmental conservation. - Lack of trust: Historical grievances and unequal benefit-sharing erode relationships. - Limited awareness of 	Highlights trust as a cornerstone of collaboration. Suggests fostering inclusive dialogue and equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms. Aligns with Social Exchange Theory, emphasising how perceptions of fairness influence stakeholder

<i>Operational Barriers</i>	<p>sustainability principles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient coordination mechanisms: Lack of communication platforms. - Challenges in community engagement: Marginalized communities feel excluded. - Resource constraints: Shortage of trained personnel and technical expertise. 	<p>willingness to collaborate (Dutt et al., 2023; Timothy, 1999). Suggests participatory frameworks and capacity-building programmes. Aligns with Ostrom's (1990) emphasis on locally tailored governance for managing common goods. Recommends clear communication channels and inclusivity to enhance stakeholder engagement, supporting Berkes (2009) and Scheyvens (1999).</p>
<i>Opportunities for Collaboration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shared interest in conserving Coyuca Lagoon and coastline. - Growing interest in community-based and ecotourism models. - Learning from successful models in other regions like Costa Rica's Monteverde Cloud Forest. 	<p>Highlights mutual recognition of shared resources as key to fostering collaboration. Recommends adapting successful participatory models to the local context. Emphasizes benefits of collaborative marketing and positioning the region as a sustainable tourism destination. Aligns with Ostrom's (1990) and Roxas et al. (2020) for sustainable tourism frameworks.</p>

5.6 Conclusion

This study examined the role of collaboration in promoting sustainable tourism in the border zone between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez, focusing on the challenges and reforms necessary for effective governance. The research was guided by two central questions, the first being – *What are the key barriers to collaboration in the context of sustainable tourism in Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez?* The findings identified significant structural, cognitive, and operational barriers. Structural barriers include weak institutional frameworks, overlapping jurisdictions, and financial disparities between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez. Cognitive barriers stem from divergent stakeholder priorities, that is, Acapulco's focus on mass tourism versus Coyuca's emphasis on community-based and environmental sustainability, along with trust issues rooted in historical grievances. Operational barriers involve a lack of formal coordination mechanisms, limited stakeholder engagement, and insufficient capacity for joint decision-making and resource management. These barriers collectively hinder collaborative efforts, reflecting broader challenges noted in the literature on fragmented governance and power imbalances (Hall, 2008; Dredge, 2006). The second question was – *What policy and institutional reforms are needed to support effective collaboration in managing shared resources?* The study highlights the need for policy reforms to establish clear governance structures and institutional mechanisms for collaboration. Joint resource management agreements, supported by formal platforms for stakeholder dialogue, are essential for fostering alignment between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez. Institutional reforms should prioritise capacity-building initiatives to empower local communities and marginalised stakeholders, ensuring their active participation in planning and decision-making processes. Additionally, financial support through public-private

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partnerships and international collaborations can address resource constraints, enabling both municipalities to invest in sustainable tourism initiatives.

5.7 Practical Advice for Managers

The findings provide actionable recommendations for tourism managers, policymakers, and practitioners seeking to improve collaboration in sustainable tourism. Developing joint resource management agreements between Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez can foster cooperation, with committees or task forces comprising representatives from both municipalities facilitating regular dialogue and coordinated decision-making.

Engaging local communities, particularly in Coyuca de Benítez, through participatory platforms can ensure their input in tourism planning and resource management. This inclusive approach can help rebuild trust and foster a sense of ownership among stakeholders. Collaborative marketing campaigns that integrate Acapulco's established tourism infrastructure with Coyuca's natural and cultural assets can attract a broader and more environmentally conscious audience.

Investing in training programmes that educate stakeholders on sustainable tourism principles and the benefits of collaboration can strengthen governance efforts. Capacity-building initiatives can equip local communities and officials with the necessary skills to actively participate in decision-making processes. Additionally, forming partnerships with NGOs, international organisations, and private sector actors can provide access to funding, technical expertise, and policy guidance, mobilising resources and driving innovation. Promoting sustainable tourism models, such as eco-lodges or community-based tours, can serve as practical demonstrations of the economic and environmental benefits of low-impact tourism. These initiatives can create a foundation for broader adoption, reinforcing the long-term viability of sustainable tourism in the region.

5.8 Research Limitations and Future Research Suggestions

The study focuses exclusively on Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez, limiting the generalizability of the findings. While many insights align with global patterns, they should be adapted to suit the specific socio-economic and environmental conditions of other regions. The qualitative methods used provided an in-depth understanding of stakeholder dynamics but limited the ability to quantify perceptions or assess broader patterns. Future research could incorporate mixed methods to complement qualitative insights with quantitative analyses. The research was conducted over a limited timeframe, which may have restricted the depth of data collection. Longitudinal studies could provide more comprehensive insights into the evolving dynamics of collaboration and the long-term impacts of governance reforms. The study sheds light on the complexities of fostering collaboration in sustainable tourism governance, particularly in regions with socio-economic disparities and divergent stakeholder priorities. While the Acapulco-Coyuca de Benitez municipal border zone faces significant structural, cognitive, and operational barriers, shared interests in resource conservation and sustainable development does offer opportunities for alignment and innovation.

Future research could explore the role of digital technologies in facilitating cross-municipal collaboration, such as using data-sharing platforms to enhance transparency and streamline decision-making. Additionally, studies focusing on the long-term impacts of collaborative initiatives on local communities' livelihoods and environmental health would provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of such approaches. By implementing targeted policy and institutional reforms, supported by participatory governance and capacity-building, stakeholders in Acapulco and Coyuca de Benítez have an opportunity to work toward a more sustainable and inclusive tourism framework. However, these efforts demand a sustained commitment from local governments, communities, and external partners—far exceeding what was observed during this study—along with the establishment of mechanisms to ensure transparency and equitable benefit-sharing.

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